

ALBINISM IN THE SNAIL-EATING SNAKE *Sibon nebulatus* (DIPSADIDAE: DIPSADINI) WITHIN AN URBAN AREA IN THE VENEZUELAN ANDES

ALBINISMO EN LA SERPIENTE CARACOLERA *Sibon nebulatus* (DIPSADIDAE: DIPSADINI) DENTRO DE UNA ZONA URBANA DE LOS ANDES VENEZOLANOS

LUIS FELIPE ESQUEDA^{1*}, SANTOS BAZÓ², JUAN CARLOS ORTÍZ³

¹Universidad de Concepción, Programa Doctorado en Sistemática y Biodiversidad, Concepción, Chile, ²Serpentario.com, Valera, Trujillo, Venezuela, ³Universidad de Concepción, Facultad de Ciencias Naturales y Oceanográficas, Departamento de Zoología, Concepción, Chile

*Correspondencia: Luis Felipe Esqueda , E-mail: luisfesqueda@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Snakes exhibit a wide repertoire of coloration patterns and designs, which themselves are subject to inherited defects, such as an abnormality in the expression of pigmentation in certain individuals. Despite being a rare phenomenon at an intrapopulation level, anomalies such as albinism and its variants have been well documented. Here, we report a juvenile individual of *Sibon nebulatus* (Linnaeus, 1758) with total albinism, the second documented record of this anomaly for the species throughout its Neotropical distribution and the first documented record in the family Dipsadidae.

KEY WORDS: Coloration pattern, chromatic aberrations, Trujillo state, northern South America.

RESUMEN

Los serpientes exhiben un amplio repertorio de patrones y diseños de coloración, los cuales de por sí están sujetos a defectos heredados como una anomalía en la expresión de pigmentación en ciertos individuos. A pesar de ser un fenómeno poco frecuente a nivel intrapoblacional, anomalías como el albinismo y sus variantes han sido bien documentados. Aquí, reportamos un individuo juvenil de *Sibon nebulatus* (Linnaeus, 1758) con albinismo total, el segundo registro documentado de esta anomalía para la especie en toda su distribución neotropical y el primer registro documentado de la familia Dipsadidae.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Patrón de coloración, aberraciones cromáticas, estado Trujillo, norte de Suramérica.

Documented records of chromatic aberrations in snakes throughout the planet are becoming more frequent (Borteiro *et al.* 2021). Although rare, albinism has been observed in almost every vertebrate species on earth, and they persist in nature even with this apparently adverse condition (McCardle 2012). Chromatophores are those cells responsible of the color by containing chromophoric substances or structures, which can be separated depending on the type of pigment (melanin or non-melanin) and their embryonic origin (Schartl *et al.* 2015). Although it is not the only one, melanin is a group of natural pigments responsible for the coloration of organisms. When exist are heritable genetic mutations through a recessive gene, the result is hypopigmentation, where the process of melanin production and synthesis in the body is suboptimal. Therefore, albinism can be defined in different ways depending on the magnitude of the hypopigmentation (see redefinition given by Borteiro *et al.* 2021). True albinism is characterized by a complete lack of melanin (Dyrkacz 1981, Griffiths *et al.* 1998, Alberts *et al.* 2004), distinguishable by the presence of red eyes, pinkish-

reddish tongue, and body coloration predominantly white, and pinkish-yellow or yellow due to another type of pigmentation not caused by melanin, but rather by carotenoid and pteridine pigments (Sazima & Di-Bernardo 1991, Bechtel 1995, Schartl *et al.* 2015).

The juvenile specimen was active at the time of sighting inside a house in the city of Valera on March 17, 2023, at 7:30 AM (9°18'35.25"N and 70°36'19.71"W, 582 m asl). The individual was sent to the serpentarium of Santos Bazó (<https://www.facebook.com/serpentariocom/>). The snake exhibits a complete absence of pigmentation in the body, including a translucent venter through which the organs are visible. It also presents reddish eyes and a pink tongue, distinctive attributes that determine a case of total albinism (Fig. 1A, B). It is curious that the documented records of chromatic aberrations are mostly in polymorphic snakes without ontogeny, but so far, it is something that will have to be addressed in the future. The species reported here does not exhibit ontogeny, and the typical color pattern is brown or light brown with

black or dark brown spots, edged with white. The dorsal surface of the head is similar to the body, while the ventral surface of the body and tail can be

variable, dark brown or light brown with or without spots (Fig. 2).

Figure 1. Juvenile specimen of *Sibon nebulatus* with total albinism. (a) Observation of the dorsal coloration of the body and eyes. (b) Note the pink color of the tongue, indicating the absence of melanin.

Figure 2. Adult specimen of *Sibon nebulatus* presenting a normal color pattern and design. Coming from way La Culata, Mérida city, Mérida state.

Borteiro *et al.* (2021) compiled a total of 115 reports of Neotropical snakes with chromatic aberrations. On the other hand, according to these authors, the only known records in the subfamily Dipsadinae correspond to species of the genera *Dipsas* (four cases), *Ninia* (one case) and *Atractus* (four cases). However, they ignore an article by Rutherford & Murphy (2013), who reported for Trinidad an adult specimen of “*Sibon nebulata*

nebulata” (= *Sibon nebulatus*) with albinism. When observing the image of this snake in life, it is clear that the dorsal coloration is not completely white, but that it presents spots whose tonality is pink or reddish, less intense than the classic reddish coloration of the eyes in aberrations previously indicated as “true albinism”. Thus, following the new classification proposed by Borteiro *et al.* (2021), this record does not seem to be total

albinism but rather amelanism. According to Rutherford & Murphy (2013), “The snake was a true albino, with the body all white with only a hint of a pattern and pinky-red eyes before preservation; after preservation the pattern and red eyes disappeared”. The absence of comments regarding the coloration of the tongue leads us to think that the *Sibon* record for Trinidad refers to a typical case of amelanism. In this sense, our Andean report shows a total absence of pigmentation (its organs are visible ventrally), including reddish eyes and a pink tongue. Therefore, it must be recognized as our report is the first dealing with albinism in the genus *Sibon* Fitzinger, 1826 and within the family Dipsadidae, since the only documented record of total albinism verified by Borteiro *et al.* (2021), corresponds to the blind snake *Amerotyphlops bronsgermianus* (Vanzolini 1976) by Mira-Mendes *et al.* (2017) and others subsequently, such as *Tomodon dorsatus* given by Ascoli-Morrete *et al.* (2021), *Tachymenis chilensis* by Urrea *et al.* (2021), *Geophis godmani* by Santamaria-Martínez *et al.* (2021) and *Geophis hoffmanni* by Mora *et al.* (2022).

Currently, the name *Sibon nebulatus sensu lato* is considered a species complex. Although Peters & Orejas-Miranda (1970) recognized four subspecies. Recently, Arteaga & Batista (2023) recognized as full species to *S. leucomelas* (Boulenger, 1836) and *S. hartwegi* Peters, 1960. Therefore, they emphasize the existence of other undescribed species related to the complex. Although the presence of *Sibon hartwegi* in the Venezuelan Andes is possible, we prefer to momentarily assign the juvenile specimen with total albinism as *Sibon nebulatus*. Despite the contribution made by Arteaga & Batista (2023), a review of the populations assigned as “*S. nebulatus*” and its geographical limits is far from being resolved at the moment. Presently, the distribution of *S. nebulatus* in the cordillera de Mérida occupies environments from 400 to 2000 m asl, both on the lacustre-andean versant and llanera-andean versant, as well as seasonal and humid environments in intramontane areas. In urban zones, it is usually easy to find it, probably due to the favorable provision of humidity and food, as the members of this genus are specialists in feeding on gastropods (Natera-Mumaw *et al.* 2015). Despite the fact that the specimen was found in the morning, they are exclusively nocturnal animals, active on the ground or among the bushes at a height of about 3 m (Natera-Mumaw *et al.* 2015). Based on their review, Sazima & Di-Bernardo (1991) found that most Neotropical snakes with albinism/leucism are preferentially nocturnal and cryptic, suggesting a

relationship to selective pressure exerted by visually oriented diurnal predators. Although there is evidence of albinism its variants in diurnal snakes and with cryptic patterns, the general trend is that found by these last authors (Sazima & Di-Bernardo 1991). In fact, the frequency of adult specimens suggests that they have been able to overcome their ecological disadvantage (e.g. Bérnils & Moira-Leite 1991, Esqueda *et al.* 2005, Espinal *et al.* 2011, Abegg *et al.* 2014, 2015, Mira-Mendes *et al.* 2017, Paredero & Passos 2020, Fernandes *et al.* 2022).

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